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D 3.2 Publication on the Pulsar Network, integrated in workflow management systems

Work Package 3

Technical References

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* *PU = Public*

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Executive Summary

Work Package 3 (WP3) of the EuroScienceGateway project comprises five tasks focused on the development and operationalization of the Pulsar Network, a distributed computing infrastructure that enables public Galaxy servers to delegate job execution to remote compute clusters provided by participating institutions.

This deliverable presents a preprint publication that describes the design, implementation, and deployment of the European Pulsar Network, with the aim of (1) enabling scalable and interoperable distributed job execution across national and European Galaxy instances, (2) simplifying infrastructure provisioning and configuration through automation frameworks, and (3) promoting sustainability and resilience by supporting shared usage and continuous monitoring of compute endpoints.

Table of contents

Disclaimer	3
Executive Summary	4
List of Abbreviations	6
1. Introduction	7
2. Results Highlights	7
3. GA4GH TES support in the Pulsar Network	8
4. Conclusions	9

List of Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Description
CVMFS	C ERN VM File S ystem
EOSC	E uropean O pen S cience C loud
EPN	E uropean P ulsar N etwork
ESG	E uro S cience G ateway (this project)
FAIR	F indable, A ccessible, I nteroperable, R eusable ¹ , a set of principles for scientific data management that emphasizes best practices and machine readability
GA4GH	G lobal A lliance for G enomics and H ealth
HPC	H igh P erformance C omputing
OI	O pen I nfrastructure
REST	R epresentational S tate T ransfer
SABER	S ystematic A PI B enchmark for pulsar E ndpoint R eliability
TES	T ask E xecution S ervice
TESP	T ask E xecution S ervice to P ulsar
VM	V irtual M achine
WP	W ork P ackage

¹ <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>

1. Introduction

The exponential growth in scientific data production has led to a steep increase in the demand for computational resources in the Life Sciences and beyond. In response, the European Union has invested significantly in the development of research computing infrastructure through strategic initiatives such as Horizon Europe, EOSC, ESFRI, and EuroHPC.

However, fragmentation across these infrastructures—due to heterogeneous hardware, software environments, workflow systems, and authorization policies—still hinders seamless interoperability and the efficient use of distributed resources. Within this context, the **EuroScienceGateway** project (Horizon Europe) has developed and deployed an innovative solution for distributed job execution in Galaxy: the **European Pulsar Network**.

This scientific work, forming the core of the deliverable, describes the design, automation strategies, and monitoring tools of the Pulsar Network, created to enable scalable, federated, and sustainable access to computational capacity for data analysis across Europe. The system supports transparent job submission for users, easy endpoint management for administrators, and a reproducible architecture based entirely on open technologies.

2. Results Highlights

The manuscript “Scaling Scientific Workflows in Europe: Architecture and Deployment of the Galaxy-Pulsar Computational Network”, presents the architecture and implementation of the **EPN**, a federated infrastructure that enables remote job execution across multiple Galaxy servers and computational backends.

Key contributions of the work include:

- **Federated and scalable architecture:** the network currently connects 13 Pulsar endpoints hosted in 10 different countries to 6 national Galaxy servers and the European Galaxy server. Endpoints can be shared across servers and added or removed dynamically.
- **Support for heterogeneous infrastructures:** Pulsar endpoints can run on public cloud platforms (e.g. Oracle Cloud), EOSC resources, or institutional clusters, offering flexibility in deployment and usage.
- **Automated deployment via Open Infrastructure tools:** infrastructure is provisioned using Terraform and configured with Ansible, enabling fully automated setup of both Galaxy servers and Pulsar endpoints.

- **Secure and interoperable communication model:** Pulsar relies on RabbitMQ using a pull-based asynchronous message system, allowing execution behind firewalls and integration with protected compute environments.
- **Efficient software and data sharing with CVMFS:** reference data, software dependencies, and container images are distributed read-only across the endpoints, ensuring consistency and minimizing redundancy.
- **Continuous monitoring with SABER:** endpoints are tested daily using real Galaxy jobs, with results publicly visualized. The SABER monitoring tool supports testing endpoints shared among different Galaxy servers and can be finely configured for debugging and validation.
- **Open, sustainable framework:** all the network components are open-source, fully versioned in GitHub, and maintained using DevOps practices (CI/CD with Jenkins, Ansible roles), ensuring traceability, reproducibility, and long-term maintainability.

3. GA4GH TES support in the Pulsar Network

The **GA4GH TES API** (<https://www.ga4gh.org/product/task-execution-service-tes/>) defines a standard interface for submitting and managing batch computing tasks across heterogeneous execution environments. To enable support for this standard within the Pulsar Network, WP3 addressed two key challenges: (1) extending Pulsar endpoints to accept job submissions via GA4GH TES, and (2) enabling workflow engines beyond Galaxy to submit jobs to Pulsar-compliant infrastructures.

To address the first objective, the **TESP** service (<https://github.com/CESNET/tesp-api>) was developed. TESP is a standalone microservice, decoupled from Pulsar itself, that implements the TES specification and acts as a translation layer between TES clients and Pulsar. It receives TES job descriptions via the standard REST API and translates them into corresponding Pulsar REST calls for execution. A key architectural feature of TESP is that data staging is delegated directly to the compute node, bypassing intermediate transfers through the TESP or Pulsar layers. Input and output files specified in the TES task are transferred end-to-end—from client-side storage to the compute node and back, following a streamlined *storage-worker-storage* pattern. The system currently supports data transfer via HTTP, FTP, and S3 protocols.

TESP can be deployed via Docker Compose in two modes:

- A **standalone mode** with an embedded Pulsar instance, ideal for testing and local execution.
- A **connected mode** that interfaces with an external Pulsar deployment, where only the TES API and supporting components are launched.

This modularity allows flexible deployments suitable for development, integration, and production environments.

To fulfill the second objective, i.e. enabling alternative Workflow Management Systems (WMS) to submit jobs to Pulsar endpoints via TES, the WfExS-backend framework has been adopted and extended.

The WfExS-backend (Workflow Execution Services backend) is a workflow orchestration layer designed to interface with GA4GH TES-compliant services, enabling execution of scientific workflows in a standardized and portable manner. Rather than modifying existing workflow engines such as Nextflow or CWLtool, WfExS introduces an intermediate translation mechanism, **TESSAP**, that intercepts container execution commands (e.g., *docker run*) and converts them into TES API requests.

TESSAP behaves like the Docker CLI for the limited subset of commands used by workflow engines, allowing these engines to run unmodified. Behind the scenes, TESSAP converts these container execution calls into TES tasks, which are then submitted to remote TES services, like TESP. This approach maintains the expected runtime environment for the engine while enabling remote, standardized execution across heterogeneous systems.

Ongoing work - The integration between **TESP** and **TESSAP** is actively being developed, with ongoing efforts focused on improving metadata exchange and provenance capture. This includes debugging and refining the collection of execution metadata, to ensure complete traceability and interoperability between the workflow engine, the TES API, and the Pulsar execution layer.

4. Conclusions

This work presents a concrete and operational model for building a federated European infrastructure for scientific data analysis that is scalable, transparent, and sustainable. Developed within the **EuroScienceGateway** project, the **European Pulsar Network** allows multiple Galaxy instances to share distributed compute resources while maintaining a seamless user experience and low administrative overhead.

By leveraging mature technologies (Galaxy, Pulsar, RabbitMQ, CVMFS), infrastructure automation (Terraform, Ansible), and integrated monitoring (SABER), the network enables robust and reproducible job execution across Europe. The framework provides tangible benefits for end users, system administrators, developers, and institutional stakeholders, promoting structured cooperation in computational resource sharing at the European level.

The preprint manuscript, “Scaling Scientific Workflows in Europe: Architecture and Deployment of the Galaxy-Pulsar Computational Network”, describing this work in detail, is available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16761933>.